

SOME COMMENTS FROM THE HISTORY OF ANCIENT EGYPT

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada Qadimgi Misr tarixi bo'yicha manbalar tahlili asosida siyosiy jarayonlar bog'liq voqea hodisalar ochishga harakat qilingan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Qadimgi Misr, poleolit, O'rta va yangi podsholik, Snofru, Xeops, Xefren, Mikerin ehromlari, Tutmos I, Tutmos III, Amenxotep II.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье на основе анализа источников по истории Древнего Египта предпринята попытка раскрыть события, связанные с политическими процессами.*

Ключевые слова: *Древний Египет, палеолит, Среднее и Новое царство, Снофру, Хеопс, Хафрен, Микерин Ехромес, Тутмос I, Тутмос III, Аменхотеп II.*

Abstract: *In this article, on the basis of the analysis of the sources on the history of Ancient Egypt, an attempt was made to uncover events related to political processes.*

Key words: *Ancient Egypt, Paleolithic, Middle and New Kingdom, Snofru, Cheops, Khafren, Mykerin Ehromes, Thutmose I, Thutmose III, Amenhotep II.*

People have lived in Egypt since the Paleolithic era. In 10-6 thousand years BC, scattered tribes living in the savannas around the Nile were engaged in gathering, hunting, and later fishing. Among them are the tribes belonging to the Kad, Sami peoples, barbarians, and Cushites, and from their intervention, the Egyptian nation was born in the 4th millennium BC. The increase in the influence of the population accelerated the transition to animal husbandry and agriculture, which led to the emergence of territorial communities [1, B.89].

It was necessary to build canals and dams for agriculture, and for this, the labor of slaves captured in internecine wars was used. As a result, social stratification took place in the community, clan nobles separated, and tribal leaders became kings. A number of small slave states emerged. Later, as a result of the struggle between them,

the kingdoms of Lower Egypt in the north and Upper Egypt in the south were formed. In about 3000 BC, both kingdoms united and formed a single state. The subsequent history of M. is divided into 4 main periods: the First Kingdom (ca. 3000-2800 BC), the Old Kingdom (ca. 2800-2250 BC), the Middle Kingdom (ca. 2050-1700 BC), the New Kingdom (ca. 1580-1070), the Late (Libya-Sais and Iran) period (about 1070-332 BC) [2, B.28].

The first tsarist period is characterized by the development of irrigation networks, the improvement of stone and copper tools, the emergence of the pottery wheel, and the development of barter trade. During this period, the state apparatus and the officials serving it - the class of secretaries - were formed, administrative districts - names were formed and they were led by nomarkhs, regular raids were organized, including to the south - to Kush (Nubia), to the north-west - to the Libyans. and campaigns against the Bedouins of the Sinai Peninsula (where there were copper mines).

During the Old Kingdom, agriculture, crafts, trade and construction continued to develop. Private land ownership appeared. The state apparatus headed by the highest official - the minister (minister) was strengthened. The pharaohs were also high priests and considered the owners of all lands and citizens. A regular army was formed, composed of community members and partly aliens (mainly the inhabitants of Kush). The idea of the absolute power of deified pharaohs was embodied in the construction of majestic mausoleums - ehamms. This was especially rampant during the III-IV dynasties (Snophru, Cheops, Khafren, Mykerin). The labor of slaves and peasants was widely used in their creation [3, B.112].

In the 23rd-22nd centuries BC, Egypt was divided into several conflicting names and small states. around 2050 under Mentuhotep I, the country was reunited under the hegemony of the city of Thebes. This city became the capital of M.

During the Middle Kingdom, representatives of the XII dynasty ruled. Large-scale irrigation works were carried out in the Fayyum oasis. Brass (bronze) items appeared. Relations with Syria, Crete, and Punt in the south increased. During the reign of Senusert III, a part of Kush (Nubia) was annexed to M. During the period of the first pharaohs of the XII dynasty, internal conflicts continued. Only during the reign of Amenemkhet III (2nd half of the 19th century) the rebellious nomarkhs were subdued and the central authority was strengthened. Ittown became the capital of M. However, increasing property stratification led to a revolt by the poor, which led to the country's further disintegration around 1750. around 1700 AD, the Hyksos invaded from the northeast and occupied most of the country for almost 110 years. Their kings who settled in Avaris formed the 15th and 16th dynasties. Local rulers survived in Thebes (XVII1 dynasty). Among the pharaohs belonging to this dynasty, Sekenenra and Kamos

started a war of liberation, which was successfully ended by their successor Yakhmos I (Amasis), the founder of the 18th dynasty. Around 1580, he expelled the Hyksos from M. After that, the restored Egyptian state was called the New Kingdom. During this period, brass began to be widely used, the first articles made of iron appeared, metalworking, weaving looms and plows were improved, wheel saws became widespread, and glassmaking developed. Raw materials were brought as tribute and barter from conquered and neighboring countries, including silver, lead, copper, timber from Syria and Palestine, gold, ivory from Kush, aromatic perfumes, and high quality saplings from Punt. An account of the fleet sent by Queen Hatshepsut to Punt has been preserved. Private slavery is extremely widespread. After successful military campaigns, 10 thousand slaves were brought. Incessant wars forced the pharaohs of the 18th-20th dynasties to think about improving the structure of the army, and the base of the army was formed by noble charioteers. A model weapon for the infantry, in particular the ulama bow, was introduced. These measures increased the fighting ability of the army. Yakhmose's successors Thutmose I, especially Thutmose III, Amenhotep II annexed Syria and Palestine in the north, and a part of Kush in the south. Regular diplomatic relations were established with the Mitanni, Babylonian and Hittite kingdoms. During the reign of Amenhotep III (2nd half of the 15th century), Egypt reached the peak of its power. The increase in the position of the temples, which received large lands, slaves, gold and other things from the pharaohs, brought the priests into conflict with the king's authority. In order to lower the status of priests and noble names, Amenhotep IV (Akhenaton) carried out religious reforms relying on small and medium landowners, in particular, he abolished the worship of old gods and introduced the worship of the only sun god - Aten. Akhenaten moved his residence to his newly built city of Akhetaton (now Al-Amarna). The struggle between the Pharaoh and the priests weakened M.; In the first half of the 14th century, it was separated from all the estates in the north. After Akhenaton's death, the priests and nobles succeeded in restoring the old religion during the reign of Pharaohs Tutankhamun and Horemheb. During the reign of Ramses I, the most famous representative of the 19th dynasty, a struggle was fought with the Hittites for the possession of Syria. In the second half of the 13th - early 12th centuries BC, during the reign of Pharaohs Merneptakh and Ramses IV, the invasion of the "Sea Peoples" and the Libyans was repelled.

Long, protracted wars have weakened Egypt economically, politically, and militarily; By the end of the 20th dynasty, the king of Syria and Kush. properties in the regions were lost. During the reign of Ramses XII (about 1070 BC), the power in Thebes actually passed into the hands of the high priest of the god Amon - Herichor [4, B.35].

In the last period (Libya - Sais and Iran), the use of iron and money circulation became widespread. In the second half of the 11th century - at the beginning of the 10th century, after the next disintegration of M., the leader of the Libyan military, Sheshoik, in the middle of the 10th century, captured the khrkimiyat in Bubastis and started the XXII dynasty. The pharaohs of this dynasty sought to unite M. into a single state. In the second half of the 8th century BC, it became subject to M. Kush (XXV dynasty), and in 671 BC it was conquered by the Assyrians. The governor of Sais, Psammetix I (663-610), succeeded in liberating and unifying the country with the help of Greek and Carian mercenaries. During the reign of him and his successor Necho II, strong trade relations were established with Greece and other countries of the Eastern Mediterranean, the settlement (colony) of Greeks was founded in Navkratis in the Delta, and the canal connecting the Nile with the Red Sea was dug; Phoenician sailors sent by Necho II circumnavigated the African continent from Shark to the West. Necho II, Psammetix II and Aprius fought with Babylon for possession of Syria and Palestine. However, weakened Egypt could not repulse the attack of Cambyses, the king of Iran, and was annexed to the Achaemenid state in 525 BC. In 331 BC, Alexander (Iskander the Great) conquered M. during his campaign against the Achaemenids. After that, Egypt became part of the Hellenistic world. The city of Alexandria, founded by Alexander the Great, became the largest commercial and cultural center. New centers of crafts and trade were established in Egypt, trade relations expanded (to Arabia and India), and the cultures of Western and Eastern countries were combined. By the end of the 2nd century BC, there was a decline in production, fewer markets, and economic and political depression. At the beginning of the 2nd century BC, M. was separated from most of its lands after the wars with the Sshavki state and Macedonia. Internal conflicts and public riots are on the rise in the country. During this period, Rome began to interfere in the internal affairs of Egypt. The Egyptian nobles tried to suppress the rioters with its help. This allowed the Romans to conquer M. by the Egyptian god Thoth, the creator of hieroglyphs (papyrus; London, British Museum). As a result, M. became a Roman province in 30 BC. After the division of the Roman Empire in 395 AD, it was a province of the Eastern Roman Empire (Byzantium). In 619, the king of Iran, Khusraw II, took advantage of the weakening of Byzantium and conquered M. Arabs conquered M. in 639-642. On the subsequent history of M., see the article Arab Republic of Egypt.

Ancient Egyptian rulers. The first kingdom. 1st dynasty: Meneye, Jer, Den, Semerkhet, 2nd dynasty: Hotep-Sexe-mui, Nebra, Peribsen, Hasekhem, Ha-sekhemui. Qad. kingdom 3rd Dynasty: Joser, Sexemjet, Neferka. 4th Dynasty (mid-28th-26th century BC): Snofru, Cheops (Khufu), Khafra (Kephren), Mykerinus (Menkaura),

Shebeyskaph. 5th dynasty (26th-25th centuries BC): Userkaf, Neferirkara, Neusera, Isesi, Una. 6th Dynasty: (mid 25th-23rd centuries BC); Teti I, Piopi I, Merenra I, Piopi II, Merenra II. 7th-8th-9th dynasties (mid-23rd-22nd centuries BC). 10th Dynasty (mid-22nd-21st centuries BC). 11th Dynasty: Antef 1 Sehertau, Menkhhoteb III Nebhepetra.

Middle Kingdom. 11th Dynasty: Mentuhotep IV Sankhkara (2015-2007), Mentuhotep V Nebtauira (2007-2000). 12th Dynasty (2000-1787): Amenemkhet I (2000-1970), Senusert I (1970-1934), Amenemkhet II (1934-1896), Senusert III (1884-1849), Amenemkhet III (1849-1801). 13th dynasty (1785-1700). 14th dynasty (before 1680). 15th and 16th (Hyksos) dynasties (1700-?). 17th dynasty (1680-1580): Senenenra, Kamos. New Kingdom. 18th Dynasty (1580-mid-14th century): Yahmose I (1580-1559), Amenhotep I (1559-1538), Thutmose I (1538-1525), Thutmose II and Hatshepsut (1523-1503), Thutmose III (1503-1491), Amenhotep III (1455-1419), Amenhotep IV (Akhnaton, 1419-1400), Tutankhamun (1400-1392), Khoremheb (mid-14th century). 19th Dynasty (1342-1206): Seti I (1337-1317), Ramses II (1290-1224). 20th Dynasty (1204-1085): Ramses IV (1204-1180), Ramses XII (1112-1070). The last kingdom (11th-4th centuries BC). 21st Dynasty (1085-950): Herichor (Thebes), Smendes (Tanis) (1035-1054). 22nd (Libyan) Dynasty (950-730): Sheshoik (950-929). Osorkon I (929-893), Takelot I (893-870), Osorkon II (870-847), Sheshoik III (823-772). 23rd Dynasty (817-730): Pe-dubast (817-763), Sheshoik IV (763-757). 24th dynasty (730-715): Bokhoris (720-715). 25th (Nubian) dynasty (751-656): Piankhi (751-716), Shabaka (716-701), Shabataka (701-689), Taharka (689-663), Tanutamun (663-656). 26th saïs (dynasty) (663-525): Psammetix I (663-610), Nexos II (610-594), Psammetix II (594-588), Aprius (588-569), Yaxmos II (569-525). 27th (Forelar) dynasty (525-404, see also Achaemenids), 28th dynasty (404-398). 29th dynasty (398-378). 30th dynasty (378-341). 31st (Fore) dynasty (341-322, see also Achaemenids).

In general, the history of ancient Egypt covers a long history and is considered one of the first places of civilization. During these periods, social, economic and political processes took place in Egypt.

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